

2. Methane ebullition from ricefields. 1992 WS.

Methane production potential of soils

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Soils in which rice is grown vary from acidic to alkaline, from deficient to toxic in terms of nutrient contents, from low organic carbon (OC) to peat soils, from sand to clay, and from ones with low base status to ones with high cation exchange capacity.

We studied the effect of soil properties in CH₄ production using 20 soils from different rice-growing areas in the Philippines. Soil properties govern the electrochemical and chemical changes that occur upon flooding and the pattern of CH₄ formation. We found that soils can be grouped into four classes according to the amount of CH₄ produced during anaerobic incubation for 10 d: I < 1 μg CH₄/g soil, II < 10, III < 100, IV > 100. Each group has a distinct pattern of CH₄ formation and differs significantly in the total amount of CH₄ produced (Fig. 1), though final Eh and pH values were similar.

Soils categorized under class IV had the highest average OC (2.2%) while those in classes I and II had average OC (1.4%). Soils with >2% OC produced more than 300 μg CH₄/g. The OC

content is the only soil property that shows a significant correlation with CH₄ production. But CH₄ production and soil OC are not correlated in soils with C content of less than 2%. Sandy soils high in OC produce more CH₄ than do clay soils. With similar OC content, the negative impact of clay is probably because of the formation of organo-mineral complexes where C becomes less degradable. Clay soils may also entrap

1. Effect of soil properties Eh and pH on CH₄ production.

more CH₄, thus increasing the probability of oxidation.

Adding rice straw increased CH₄ production but did not affect the grouping of the CH₄ production potential of the soils (Fig. 2). This implies that degradable C is an important-but not the only-limiting factor for CH₄ production.

Soils that produced the highest CH₄ had low pH when air-dried. This appears to contradict the hypothesis that acidic soils produce less CH₄. The reduction of soils upon flooding converges any air-dried soil pH at about 7, which is the optimum level for CH₄ production. In acid soils, substrates that can be catabolized by methanogens may be conserved during the fallow periods and the initial reduction phase, leading to higher total CH₄ production.

The effects of soil properties on CH₄ production and oxidation are not well-understood at present. Further research is needed to elucidate the dynamic and

CH₄ (µg/g soil)

2. Effect of adding straw on CH₄ production 20 d after flooding. 1992 WS.

complex interaction of microbial metabolism of the whole fermentation chain and soil properties to determine mechanistically the CH₄ production potential of soils. ■

Predicting methane production in wetland rice soils

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Methane is an important greenhouse gas with a relative potential for thermal absorption 30 times greater than that of CO₂. It plays an important role in the chemistry of the troposphere. Methane production in soil is a microbiological process that occurs under strict anaerobic conditions. Soil oxidation - reduction (redox) characteristics are the key soil parameters that control CH₄ production.

Laboratory incubation studies were conducted using 10 wetland rice soils from the Philippines to measure patterns of soil reduction upon wetting. The following logarithmic function was used to quantify soil reduction patterns of soil redox potentials (Eh):

$$y = a + b \ln x$$

where y = Eh at a given time, a = equilibrium Eh for the system, b = rate of reduction, and x = days after flooding.

The reduction capacity of the soil was defined as the difference between the fitted initial Eh and equilibrium Eh values. (See Figure 1 for the fitted and observed Eh values for the soils). Given the excellent description of Eh, the fitted data were used in subsequent analysis. The rate and capacity of soil on wetting strongly influenced CH₄ production (Fig. 2).

The C-N ratio of labile organic matter controlled the reduction rate upon

1. Measured soil redox potentials (Eh, mV) compared with fitted values obtained using a logarithmic function.

wetting, whereas the reduction capacity of the soils was negatively correlated to the active iron, cation exchange capacity, and clay, silt, and sand content.

Predicting CH₄ production upon wetting depends on the rate and capacity for reduction in soils when melted. Initial results suggest that the nature of labile organic matter, buffering due to iron compounds, and soil texture control the soil reduction process. ■

2. Methane production (log, µg CH₄/g soil) during a 30-d incubation predicted from the rate and capacity of soil reduction.